

SYNTHESIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES IN THE SOLUTION OF HYDROXYPROPYLMETHYLCELLULOSE BASED ON NANOFIBER MAT

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Silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) have drawn intensive interest in recent years due to the low-cost, high-efficiency, unique antibacterial and antifungal properties which lead to potential applications in pharmaceutical industrial fields such as antiseptics, antimicrobial agents, disinfectant agents [1].

Hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC) is the most important hydrophilic carrier material used for the preparation of oral controlled drug delivery systems [2]. One of its most important characteristics is the high swell ability, bio durability, solubility which has a significant effect on the release kinetics of an incorporated drug. Upon contact with water or biological fluid the latter diffuses into the device, resulting in polymer chain relaxation with volume expansion [3].

Electrospinning, as an electrohydrodynamic technique, is broadly exploited to treat cellulose and its derivatives for biomedical and other applications [4].

A single-step and straightforward operation of electrospinning on a co-dissolving solution of a cellulose derivative and a drug can bring out medicated nanoproducts with unique properties for targeted applications, which have been demonstrated in many investigations [5].

The aim of this study was to formation of Ag NPs in the solution of HPMC based on nanofibers mat by electrospinning and study their physico-chemical characteristics.

Silver nanoparticles were produced in water by reduction of silver nitrate with glucose in the presence of HPMC. During the preparation, reducing agent's glucose directly reduced silver ions to metallic silver atoms. The silver atoms then precipitated to form Ag NPs with HPMC absorbed on the surface of the Ag NPs.

The green synthesis of AgNPs, using HPMC and glucose as capping agents and reducing agents respectively, is an environmental friendly, simple and efficient route for synthesis of nanoparticles.

Reaction temperature, reaction time and the concentration of silver source and reducing agents play important roles in size, shape and yields of Ag NPs.

The structure, size and polydispersity of the prepared Ag NPs was studied by TEM, AFM which showed the rather wide size distribution of the prepared Ag NPs. Most of the particles were found to be smaller about 10-50 nm in diameter.

It was established that the silver cations within HPMC macromolecules can play role as stabilizations for the AgNPs. The form and size of AgNPs within HPMC solution and films were controlled. Depending on the concentration of the HPMC, glucose, Ag⁺ and reaction conditions, the spherical and rod-like Ag NPs are formed and stabilized by HPMC.

The prepared biodegradable HPMC films containing Ag NPs are of interest as bactericidal and bacteriostatic coatings for the treatment of burns and trophic ulcers.

The spin ability of HPMC was increased after formation of Ag NPs. Using HPMC as raw materials, deionized water as solvent and Ag NPs as complex formation agent, nanofiber membranes were prepared by electrospinning method. Furthermore, the

morphology of nanofibers was optimized by adjusting the solute ratio and solvent concentration, and the experimental parameter was finally determined as 2 wt.% HPMC solution: 0,00324 wt.% AgNO₃ solution, 0,053 wt.% glucose solution, the working voltage was 23kV, the distance between the receiving device and the spinning device was 10 cm, and the spinning speed was 2 μL·h⁻¹, the nanofiber membrane with uniform and regular morphology was obtained.

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